

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The present paper describes the use of a continuum fracture mechanics approach to assess the interlaminar toughness of fibre-composite materials. Various test techniques have been employed to measure the mode I (tensile), mode II (in-plane shear) and mixed-mode I/II fracture energies for carbon-fibre composites based upon epoxy, polybismaleimide and poly(ether-ether ketone) matrices. In particular, a new test method is proposed which enables the values of these parameters to be deduced from a single test specimen and a new mixed-mode fracture criterion is derived from first principles which quantitatively describes the failure locus.

INTRODUCTION

The propagation of interlaminar defects is extremely damaging to the performance of fibre-composite materials. Such delaminations may not only lead to complete fracture of the structure but even partial delaminations will lead to a loss of stiffness which can be an important design consideration. Initial defects are often quite small and can arise from voids arising during the materials production, e.g. incomplete wetting of the fibres by the matrix, or from damage during subsequent service, e.g. impact damage. However, when the material is loaded these defects may propagate to give a major deterioration in performance. Thus, a knowledge of the crack growth behaviour is essential for material development and selection and for design and life-prediction studies. A popular approach to the characterisation of the propagation of interlaminar cracks has been through the application of linear-elastic fracture-mechanics (LEFM) which enables the critical energy-release rate or fracture energy, G_c , to be deduced.

Mode I (tensile) is the lowest fracture energy mode for isotropic materials and, thus, a crack always propagates along a path normal to the direction of maximum principal tensile stress. Hence, a crack in an isotropic plate will propagate in mode I fracture regardless of the orientation of the initial flaw with respect to the applied stress. However, this is not necessarily the case for crack growth in fibre-composites which are highly anisotropic materials. In these materials the initial interlaminar defect is constrained and usually continues to propagate in the same plane between the laminae regardless of the orientation of the crack to the applied loads. Thus, genuine mode II (in-plane shear) failures are possible and, obviously, mixed-mode I/II failures may also be observed. There has been therefore considerable interest [1-3] in determining values of G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and $G_{I/IIc}$ and modelling the data in order to derive a fracture criterion which quantitatively describes the experimental observed failure locus. Nevertheless, the scatter recorded from such experiments has been

large and this has hindered the development of a failure criterion, and the criteria which have been advanced have been largely empirical in nature.

The present paper attempts to examine interlaminar crack propagation in detail and seeks to develop a more rational basis for a mixed-mode criterion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The materials used in the study were;

(i) carbon-fibre/poly(ether-ether ketone) (PEEK) composite (ICI 'APC2'): the fabrication of laminates consisting of 0° graphite/PEEK tape was performed by ICI. The laminates consisted of 24 and 48 plies giving thicknesses of 3mm and 6mm respectively.

(ii) carbon-fibre/epoxy composite (Ciba Geigy 'Fibredux 6376C'): thirty-two ply panels were laid up using prepreg tape containing continuous unidirectional carbon-fibre filaments with a nominal resin content of 35%. The panels were cured at 140°C in accordance with the suppliers specifications and the cured laminate thickness was about 4mm. The resin glass transition temperature, T_g , was 140°C .

(iii) carbon-fibre/polyimide composite (Technochemie rubber-toughened polybismaleimide [4]): sixteen ply panels were laid up using prepreg tape containing continuous unidirectional carbon-fibre filaments with a nominal resin content of 35%. All laminae had the same fibre orientation in the laminate. The panel was then cured at 190°C and postcured at 240°C in accordance with the suppliers specifications. The cured laminate thickness was about 2mm. The resin glass transition temperature, T_g , was about 300°C .

Test specimens

Mode I - the test specimen employed to determine the mode I fracture energy, G_{Ic} , was the familiar double-cantilever beam (DCB) specimen loaded by applying symmetrical opening tensile forces at the ends of the beam, as shown in Figure 1(a). G_{Ic} was calculated using the relationship:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{12 P_c^2 a^2}{E B^2 D^3} = \frac{3 P_c \delta}{2 B a} \quad (1)$$

where P_c is the load, B =specimen thickness, D =half the total depth, a =crack length, δ =loadline displacement and E =Young's modulus.

Mode II - the test specimen used to measure G_{IIc} was a DCB specimen loaded asymmetrically, as shown [2] in Figure 1(b). G_{IIc} was calculated using the following equation:

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{3 P_c^2 a^2}{16 B E I} \quad (2)$$

where I is the second moment of area and $I=BD^3/12$

Mixed-mode III (fixed ratio) - the test specimen shown in Figure 1(c) was used to obtain a value of $G_{I/IIc}$ for mixed-mode crack propagation and the values of the separate G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m contributions at fracture may be deduced from the following equations:

$$G_{Ic}^m = \frac{P_c^2 a^2}{4 B E I} \quad , \quad G_{IIc}^m = \frac{3 P_c^2 a^2}{16 B E I} \quad (3)$$

However, this test specimen only results in one fixed ratio of mode I to mode II of 1.33:1.

Mixed-mode III (varying ratio) - the new design of test specimen shown in Figure 1(d) has been used to obtain the values of G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m for mixed-mode failure but the design is such that the ratio of mode I to II will vary according to the ratios of a/L and a/l that are selected, as indicated on the Figure. Hence, for a given geometry, the mode I to II ratio will change as the crack propagates and the value of a increases. This enables a large number of pairs of values of G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m to be deduced at different mode I to II ratios from the one test. G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m values are calculated using the following relationships:

$$G_{Ic}^m = \frac{\left[P_c l \left[1 - \left[l/a \right]^2 \right] \right]^2}{16 B E I} \quad , \quad G_{IIc}^m = \frac{3 \left[P_c l \left[1 - a/L \right] \right]^2}{16 B E I} \quad (4)$$

note that when the ratios of a/L and a/l are unity then pure mode I and pure mode II respectively results, so that the values of G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} may also be determined. This test specimen therefore enables a complete spectrum of fracture energy values to be measured.

In all the above specimens the initial starter crack was formed by moulding a small length of release-coated aluminium foil into the centre layer of the composite and a 'natural' crack was then propagated from the foil for a short distance before measurements were undertaken. The tests were conducted on an Instron tensile testing machine at a constant displacement rate of 2 mm/min. To monitor the position of the crack front, the edge of the sample was painted white and marked at 5mm spacings. The load on each specimen was monitored as a function of time using the Instron chart recorder. The displacement versus time was calculated from the crosshead speed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Load-displacement relations

Typical Load-versus displacement traces from the four different test specimens using the poly(ether-ether ketone) based composite are shown schematically in Figure 2. There are several noteworthy features. Firstly, the load-displacement traces for mode I and the mixed-mode indicate both continuous and stick/slip types of crack growth behaviour, whereas only continuous crack growth behaviour was noted for mode II tests. Secondly, the load-displacement traces for mode II and the mixed-mode exhibit some degree of nonlinearity prior to the maximum load, indicating crack growth occurring before the maximum load is

reached. To examine this further a few specimens were loaded in mode II and in mixed-mode and were subsequently unloaded prior to the peak load. These specimens were then broken open and their fracture surfaces examined. It was evident from the fracture surfaces that the onset of crack growth (initiation) occurs prior to the maximum load but that it occurs close to the point of nonlinearity in the load-displacement trace.

In the case of the polybismaleimide and epoxy based composites only continuous crack growth behaviour was observed.

"R" curves

From the above load versus displacement traces the respective fracture energies were calculated using the relationships stated previously. Of particular interest is the possibility of the value of the fracture energy being dependent upon the increment of crack growth that has occurred at the instant the fracture energy is deduced. In some materials, especially relatively tough materials, the value of the measured fracture energy increases as the crack grows, at a steady rate, and the relationship is referred to as an "R" curve. Such a relationship typically arises because the extent of the plastic-deformation zone at the crack tip increases as the crack grows, and this is reflected in the value of the fracture energy increasing. In composite materials one might also envisage the degree of fibre-bridging behind the crack tip increasing as the crack propagates and this might also result in an "R" curve being recorded.

The fracture energies versus crack growth increment, Δa , are illustrated in Figure 3 respectively for the test specimens shown in Figures 1a-d; note : $G_{I/IIc} = G_{Ic}^m + G_{IIc}^m$. The main points of interest are, firstly, for the mode I test there is no indication of an "R" curve and therefore the value of G_{Ic} for crack propagation may be unambiguously stated. Secondly, in the cases of the mode II and mixed-mode I/II (fixed ratio) tests there are clear signs of an "R" curve and the values of G_{IIc} and $G_{I/IIc}$ (and corresponding values of G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m) have been taken as the values for $\Delta a \rightarrow 0$.

Values of the fracture energies

The values of the pure mode I and mode II fracture energies, G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} respectively, for the various composites are shown in Table 1. These values were obtained using the test specimens shown in Figures 1(a) and 1(b) respectively.

For the poly(ether-ether ketone)/carbon-fibre composite not only pure mode I and II fracture energies, i.e. G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} , have been measured but also mixed-mode values, i.e. G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m , have been determined using both the fixed ratio and the new, variable ratio, test specimen. The data are shown in Figure 4 and several interesting points emerge. Firstly, for the new mixed-mode test (Figure 1(d)) the data ascertained from using different values of l are in excellent agreement. Secondly, the values of G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m determined from the new test method are in good agreement with those from the fixed-ratio mixed-mode test, when the former test is arranged to give the same ratio as the latter test always maintains. Thirdly, the values of the pure mode I fracture energy, G_{Ic} , from the new test when $a = L$ (see Figure 1(d)) are in good agreement from those derived from the symmetrically-loaded DCB test (Figure 1(a)). Thus, the new test method appears to yield valid values not only of G_{Ic} but also of $G_{I/IIc}$ (and the separate components G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m) over a very wide range of mode I to II ratios.

Typical scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces from mode I, mode II and mixed-mode (43% mode II) tests on poly(ether-ether-ketone)/carbon fibre composite are shown in Figure 5. It is of interest to note that as the degree of mode II fracture increases there is an increasing extent of interfacial failure between the matrix and fibres.

Fracture criterion

Having obtained the data shown in Figure 4 it is obviously of interest and importance to seek a model to quantitatively describe the failure locus. The simplest is that the total fracture energy remains constant:

$$G_c = G_{Ic}^m + G_{IIc}^m \quad (5)$$

but this requires that $G_{Ic} = G_{IIc}$ and this is clearly not true, from both the present data shown in Table 1 and previous data reported [3] in the literature. This has led to empirical modifications of this type of criterion to give forms such as:

$$\left[\frac{G_{Ic}^m}{G_{Ic}} \right]^\eta + \left[\frac{G_{IIc}^m}{G_{IIc}} \right]^\beta = 1 \quad (6)$$

where η and β are constants and G_{Ic} does not now have to equal G_{IIc} .

To seek a more rational basis for a criterion for crack propagation we have developed [5] a criterion based upon the concept of attaining a critical crack opening displacement, δ , at the crack tip. The criterion is based upon an interlaminar crack with a plastic or damage line-zone of length r_p which is subjected to both tensile and shear stresses, see Figure 6. Essentially, the criterion supposes that crack propagation occurs either when the local mode I crack opening displacement attains a critical value, i.e. when $\delta_T = \delta_{Tc}$, or when the local mode II crack opening displacement attains a critical value, i.e. when $\delta_S = \delta_{Sc}$. Thus, when crack propagation occurs under mode I control:

$$\delta_T = \delta_{Tc} = \frac{G_{Ic}}{\sigma_y} = \frac{G_{Ic}^m}{\sigma_T} \quad (7)$$

and when under mode II control:

$$\delta_S = \delta_{Sc} = \frac{\sqrt{3} G_{IIc}}{\sigma_y} = \frac{G_{IIc}^m}{\tau_S} \quad (8)$$

where σ_y is the tensile yield stress and σ_T and τ_S are the tensile and shear stresses in the zone, Figure 6. Now, using the Dugdale plastic-zone model and the known relationships between the stress-intensity factors in Modes I and II and the corresponding fracture energies, it may be shown [5] that, from the mode I criterion, we may obtain the relationship:

$$\Gamma_{IIc} = \frac{1}{3\psi} \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma_{Ic}} \cdot \Gamma_{Ic} \right] \quad (9)$$

and from the mode II fracture criterion:

$$\Gamma_{Ic} = 3\psi \left[\frac{\alpha^2}{\Gamma_{IIc}} \cdot \Gamma_{IIc} \right] \quad (10)$$

where: $\Gamma_{Ic} = G_{Ic}^m / G_{Ic}$, $\Gamma_{IIc} = G_{IIc}^m / G_{IIc}$, $\alpha = G_{IIc} / G_{Ic}$ and $\psi = (E_1/E_2)^{1/2}$ and E_1 and E_2 are the local moduli in the directions 1 and 2, see Figure 6.

Now equations (9) and (10) may be used to deduce the mixed-mode failure locus from values of G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and the modulus ratio E_1/E_2 . The value of this last term is that which applies locally to the regions around the crack tip. Very close to the crack tip it will possess a value of 1, whilst at regions distant from the crack tip it will assume the value of about 25. At the present time it is not clear how best to assign the value of this modulus ratio and in Figure 4 the theoretical failure locus is drawn for different values of E_1/E_2 .

The initial agreement between the experimental data and the theoretical relations is very encouraging and the use of a critical crack opening displacement criterion, one governing mode I fracture and one governing mode II fracture, will be explored further.

CONCLUSIONS

Values of the fracture energies in mode I, mode II and mixed-mode (mode I/II) have been determined. A new test method has been developed which enables not only values of G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} to be readily determined but also values of G_{Ic}^m and G_{IIc}^m (where $G_{I/IIc} = G_{Ic}^m + G_{IIc}^m$) to be assessed over a wide range of mode I to mode II ratios. The results from this new test method agree well with those from other established techniques.

A fracture criterion has been proposed which quantitatively describes the observed failure locus of G_{Ic}^m versus G_{IIc}^m . This criterion is based upon the concept of a critical crack opening displacement controlling the onset of crack propagation and supposes that fracture occurs either under mode I control when $\delta_T = \delta_{Tc}$ or under mode II control when $\delta_S = \delta_{Sc}$.

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TABLE 1
Values of G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} for the various composites

Composite matrix	Test temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	Fracture energies (kJ/m^2)	
		G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}
Polybismaleimide	20	0.18	-
	60	0.21	-
	100	0.19	-
	130	0.22	-
	200	0.22	-
Epoxy	20	0.31	0.76
	60	0.35	-
	100	0.42	-
Poly(ether-ether ketone)	20	2.30-2.50	2.3
	60	2.85	2.7
	100	3.87	2.7
	130	5.10	2.7

(a) MODE I

(c) MIXED MODE (FIXED RATIO)

(b) MODE II

(d) NEW VARIABLE MIXED MODE

Figure 1. Loading configurations.

Figure 2. schematic representation of the load-displacement curve for poly(ether-ether-ketone) at +20°C for the four different test specimens.

Figure 3. G versus Δa curves for poly(ether-ether-ketone)/carbon fibre composite at +20°C

Figure 4. Values of G^m_{Ic} and G^m_{IIc} for poly(ether-ether ketone)/carbon fibre composite at 20°C for various l values ($L=254\text{mm}$).
 (\square $l=4.5$ inch, \diamond $l=3$ inch, \triangle $l=2.5$ inch)

- theoretical curves are for different ψ values ($\psi=(E_1/E_2)^{1/2}$) for mode I controlled fracture.

- closed points are for the data obtained from pure mode I, G_{Ic} ; pure mode II, G_{IIc} and fixed mixed- mode ratio ($G_{Ic}/G_{IIc}=4/3$) tests.

MODE I

MIXED MODE (FIXED RATIO)

MODE II

1mm=0.5 μ m

Figure 5. Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces of poly(ether-ether ketone)/carbon fibre composite at 20°C in (a) mode I, (b) mode II, (c) mixed mode (fixed ratio)

Figure 6. Plastic-line zone in a laminate under mixed-mode (mode I/II) loads.